

**INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ
ЯЗЫКУ**

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Abstract: the role and the effective usage of innovative technologies in teaching English are considered in this article. The Internet links, which are effectively used during the lessons, are also shown here.

Аннотация: в данной статье рассматриваются роль и эффективное применение инновационных технологий в обучении английскому языку, также указаны ссылки на интернет-ресурсы, эффективно применяемые на уроках.

Keywords: innovative technologies, multimedia, Internet links, electronic resources, learning environment, motivation.

Ключевые слова: инновационные технологий, мультимедиа, интернет ссылки, электронные ресурсы, обучающая среда, мотивация.

Today, our country dictates new tasks of social modernization, industrialization and accelerated innovation challenges in the new global economic integration. The main objective of the third decade of the XXI century of independent Uzbekistan is to move forward to joining the top 30 developed countries of the world. 78 In this regard, there is a great responsibility on educated and highly qualified young people of Uzbekistan, such as the development of national competitiveness in the XXI century, providing prosperity and universal recognition of the country all over the world. In the Annual Presidential Address of

the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Strategy Uzbekistan-2050": "New political course of the established state" is observed that the education system should be modernized and noted "We expect to implement modernization of teaching methods and actively develop online education systems, creating regional school centers. We should intensively introduce innovative methods, solutions and tools into the home, including the distance education and online education that is affordable for all...". The role of innovation in education is great. The effective use of Innovative technologies, such as computers, the Internet, multimedia resources in the educational process is the only way to show the quality of education. One of the innovative technologies of improving the students' communicative abilities is using multimedia in the process of teaching and learning in the classroom. Proper use of multimedia in classroom will provide the opportunity for interacting with diverse texts that give students a solid background in the tasks and content of mainstream courses. Furthermore, because educational technology is expected to become an integral part of the curriculum, students must become proficient in accessing and using electronic resources. In terms of providing educational institutions with multimedia products, there are some problems to be solved so far: • the virtual absence of domestic electronic textbooks (ET) in official language at educational institutions; • lack of effectiveness of using the existing electronic textbooks; • poor quality of teacher training in using electronic textbooks; • insufficient implementation of new educational technologies in the educational process; • low efficiency of automated assessment system in teaching. The using of multimedia in classroom cannot be denied anymore. That will make possible for teachers giving more opportunity to students being happier and more enjoy during the learning course. Through their interactions with multimedia texts, students become increasingly familiar with academic vocabulary and language structures. As they pursue sustained study of one content area through focus discipline research, the students become actively engaged in the process of meaning construction within and across different media. Learners obtain most of the information from electronic devices, which has made such tools, a very essential component of their daily life.

Using innovative technologies in a classroom as a tool for language learning has many benefits. It gives stimulus to undertake the tasks. And could help in creating a long lasting impact on the learners. The role of teacher will change from an instructor's role to a coordinator. Self-paced independent learning methodology is what is being propagated with the help innovative technologies in English Language Teaching. Using multimedia provides the students to gather information through media that encourages their imaginations, interests. One of the main problems faced by the language teacher, especially newcomers to the profession, is that methodology refuses to stand still. As McCarthy puts it: The methodology of foreign language teaching has evolved dramatically over the past half century, with emphasis at different times being placed on a remarkable array of philosophies and approaches under banners such as grammar-translation, audio-lingual, structuro-global audiovisual, inductive/deductive, functional, notional, situational, communicative, immersion, learning/acquisition, suggestopedia, directivist/constructivist, etc. Although each approach has seen its share of zealous purists, it would seem that, viewed from a distance, the abiding lesson to teachers has been that no one approach is a magic wand capable of transforming any class of foreign language learners into near-native speakers of the target language, and that each approach brings to the fore a previously neglected or forgotten facet. As language teachers, we have a tradition of integrating new media into our teaching. We have embraced any new technology, which was likely to improve learning. Mindful of the need to bring native speaker voices into the classroom, teachers in the first half of the 20th century took gramophones into their classrooms. These were replaced by reel-to-reel tape recorders when the price was right and appropriate recordings became available. Brave souls acquired microphones and encouraged students to record their own voices, to accustom them to hearing themselves speaking in another language. The next innovation was the language laboratory, coming as it did at a time when the audio-lingual method was to the fore and drills were considered central to successful language learning. Those entrusted with the maintenance of language laboratories heaved a sigh of relief when

audiocassette recorders replaced reel-to-reel tape. Slide and filmstrip projectors, film projectors and television sets also found their way into language classrooms, followed by video players and video cameras. All of these innovations made their entrance as "bolt-ons". It was only when their characteristics were fully understood and their strengths identified in comparison with existing media that they become integrated into the delivery strategy of the teachers concerned, and into published courses [3].

79 So, why do I use multimedia materials in the classroom? First, it helps to enhance understanding. Valuable media materials boost student comprehension of complex topics, especially dynamic processes that unfold over time. At second, it increases memorability – rich media materials lead to better encoding and easier retrieval. The most important advantage is that media helps to improve their four language skills like listening, reading, speaking and writing. Moreover, information technology develops students' critical thinking. Furthermore, multimedia provides us with individualized learning, which means that multimedia resources can help you meet needs of many different types of learners. Like, Visual learners can watch a video, while auditory learners listen to streaming audio hands-on learners play and interactive game. Students who need extra practice can use online exercises to improve their grammar or vocabulary skills. In my opinion, multimedia resources can help our students to experience today's global community. With multimedia students can learn about new cultures and countries in immediate and authentic ways – and prepare to interact with that broader community. In addition, the last three points show that multimedia is oriented towards the learner's cultural background and addressing students' learning needs. Information and communication technologies are the most important parameter of contemporary socio-cultural system. Online Resources are familiar and convenient means of exploring the culture of other countries and peoples, communication, information, inexhaustible source of educational process. That is why, based on a systematic approach to reforming the methods of learning a foreign language using the new information technologies based on the concept of information and learning environment, which is seen in close connection with the system of developmental

education. Information - learning environment is a set of conditions that not only let us create and develop language skills, abilities and skills, but also promote the development of the individual student. Multimedia technology could significantly enhance student's capability in problem solving and in learning by doing. Computers increased students' opportunities for self-directed learning. In another study carried out by Vernadakis and colleague [2008], they found that multimedia could help language learners' motivation, support their language skills, affect their learning attitude, and build their self-confidence through various communicative and interactive activities. Their findings indicated that the multimedia language courseware, by providing the test items, allows every individual to assess their own learning components confidently. Participation in information - communication pedagogical activity promotes the integrated development of all aspects of communicative competence: linguistic, socio-cultural, cognitive, linguistic-country study; as well as related cognitive - communicative abilities of pupils (search and selection of relevant information, its analysis, synthesis and classification). Modeling of real authentic environment by attracting Internet - resources is not only a successful development of the language, but also allows you to understand the fundamental laws of the unity and diversity of culture. In additionally, we want to share with useful teaching Internet links for ELT: 1. English Tutor Bournemouth The website provides free resources for teachers and students on a range of GCSE and 'A' Level texts. Key quotations, annotated poetry, character profiles, worksheets etc. The site has a second purpose, which is to offer private tutoring services. 2. Book Box from Channel 4 Learning Features interviews with leading children's authors, poets, illustrators. Suggestions for reading with reviews and excerpts. Templates for pitching the film of the book. 3. BBEC ENG DEPT An ever-growing collection of links for teachers of English and their students. 4. Easy Read Shakespeare Easy Read Shakespeare is a new version of Shakespeare's plays formatted in a way to make them easier to follow from the printed page. Character portraits are used to help the reader follow the conversations and location drawings help set the scene. A great resource for anyone studying Shakespeare who can't get

to see the plays. 5. Hope Education Broad range of English teaching materials including books, speaking and listening tools, phonics and story packs 6. Literary Connections links, books and resources for secondary English - mainly but not exclusively for literature. 7. Teacher's Pet Text Tool for Teachers is a free add-on for Microsoft Word that can help you transform any text into a fun classroom activity. Developed by a teacher, here are just some of the things the tool can do: Crosswords Flashcards Bingo Cards Jumbles Gap-fill / Cloze tests. Thus, the innovative technologies that we reviewed today significantly enrich and diversify the teaching of foreign languages. In place of the monotonous work comes intelligent creative search, during which formed a new type of personality, active and purposeful, focused on constant self-education and development.

References

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